

APPLICATION OF HEALTHY GYMNASTIC EXERCISES TO ELDERLY PEOPLE

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Abstract. The article constantly illustrates the limitation of gymnastics, the limitation of their efforts, the deterioration of physical and mental health, and the improvement of the quality of movements.

Key words: old age, health exercises, experience, active lifestyle, breathing exercises.

ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ЗДОРОВЫХ ГИМНАСТИЧЕСКИХ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ У ПОЖИЛЫХ ЛЮДЕЙ

Аннотация. В статье постоянно иллюстрируется ограниченность занятий гимнастикой, ограниченность их усилий, ухудшение физического и психического здоровья, улучшение качества движений.

Ключевые слова: пожилой возраст, оздоровительные упражнения, опыт, активный образ жизни, дыхательная гимнастика.

Introduction. Last ten in annuals not only Maybe in Uzbekistan whole in the world aged of the population the number increased is going Big ages and old age people 62 percent organize that 's enough our of our country to labor capable from the age increased each the fourth population Old people own problems solution to do for special the approach Demand who does individual , demographic, social and medical and biological to the category became [3].

The elderly health getting worse going of a person physical and spiritual health strengthening new , effective tools and physical education methods to search Demand does _

Old of people main the problem is mobility limited, physical and spiritual of health deterioration. This the problem learning the elderly at home inhabitant (su including own _ in their homes residents too) of people in most cases locomotion system diseases presence , some in patients self treatment ability lack of with is based on Healthier gymnastics a person to the body useful effect shows . The elderly for healthy gymnastics many of diseases prevention get and in treatment help also provides rehabilitation __ process accelerates. Energy effect whole in the body done is increased. Healthier gymnastics using each one to a person special has been self recovery mechanisms to work is dropped and engage in in the process common physical and spiritual of the situation to normalization reach can _

The elderly for healthy exercises complex , even exercises upright standing without do it those who do not for too available _ for example , sitting or lying down patients for is also This gymnastics to the elderly health status and preparation from the level strictly look , physical activity continue to continue possibility gives [2].

Research purpose _ Big age and old age people with of training efficient methodology work exit _

Research methods : " Movement this life " experience the elderly and disabled people for 2022 _ from March until November has been at the time the elderly at home was conducted .

Participants Number : 25 people . Group of members age : from 45 years old big _

Experience for residents two to the group divided into : " Active " and " Passive " section . to the " Active " group physical activity high has been to himself service to show able people to the " Passive " group and to himself service to do able individual approach to lessons _ Demand those who do entered . Old people at home of the inhabitants average age 69 years was _

First stage - "Participation achieve". This of stage purpose the elderly in the middle physical education, active life style with engage in motivation formation and development the elderly _ psychological is support . The elderly at home residents of the body functional status according to studies conducted : anthropometric measurements on " Medass " and "Omega S" devices studies .

The first " Participation at the "achievement" stage 12 lessons in the first " Active " group (3 lessons per week), 12 lessons in the " Passive " group offer done _

The second "Spring " phase is in May At the end of being passed . This stage main attention aerobic to exercises focused , therefore for program regularly walking , breathing get exercises , warming up and to cool down own into received _

The last one is the "Autumn" final stage from October until November continue did _ This in the step " Open in the air games ", physiotherapy exercises , coordination exercises such as to training connected .

Groups for healthy gymnastics from exercises organize found methodology used : self massage do , articulate gymnastics , biological active points hold , breath get exercises , physiotherapy and walking exercises such as

Functional of indicators change dynamics determination for the elderly with the following studies held : anthropometric measurements , hardware technologies , psychological tests and questions . Research results in the minutes note done _

All measurements mathematician processing given _

Equipment methods : of the patient eating situation assessment , obesity and metabolic of the syndrome deep diagnosis to spend , to eat protein structural part of sufficiency evaluation of the patient movement activities assessment , physical development evaluation enable ABC Medass that gives bioimpedance analyzer according to studies , in the body violations detection , chronic catabolic of diseases wide scope detection [21].

Physical the situation objective evaluation Specialized hardware and software for Omega-S complex according to studies was conducted . of the "Omega-S" complex constant respectively accumulated standing electron data base physical in the case deviations fast note reach enable will give and that's it with injury risk reduces _

Physiological development indicators anthropometric of measurements the following methods used : height (cm), weight (kg), chest volume - calm in case breath get and breath release _ Difference is the breath get type and muscles How developed depends wrist dynamometer using hand muscles power was measured .

Biomedical dimensions (functional tests). Pedagogical observation training during of subjects functional the state of the body objective parameters control of doing main methods as used _ Physical exercises during the following measured: heart hit _ arterial pressure .

Results and him discussion do :

Experience before anthropometric information : the elderly at home living of the elderly average 156 centimeters tall organize did _ average weight - 58 kilograms ; arterial pressure systole

- 133 millimeters mercury ; blood pressure diastole - 68 mm. rt. from _ calm in the case heart beats
- 68 times per minute; left hand of strength dynamometry - 11 kilograms; right hand of strength dynamometry - 14 kg EG apparatus technologies with take went studies results and analyzes "MEDASS" apparatus according to the body content evaluation experience in the group the following the results showed :

Fatigue-5%;

Fitness standard -10 %; Norm - 15%;

Too much weight - 40 %; Obesity - 20%.

"Medass" device the results analysis by doing that's it to say possibly of fat mass share experience in the group experience from the transfer before enough not , too except a lot in quantity fat compound 40 % and 20% diagnosis of obesity enable gives Body normal indicators of fat percentage range two to the degree divided into: "normal" 15% and "fitness standard " 10%, that is high and bottom to intervals right will come

" Fat leaving " diagnosis fat mass _ percent values with both, the body mass of the index values also put on can _ Too much fat mass is 20 kg organize did _

So of markers _on the scales fat and _locomotion mass didn't happen status hypersthenic type means that _while heart-blood veins and motor mounts to the situation looking diet to therapy addition as aerobic physical activity recommendation reach enable gives _ Big old and old age of people health about information analysis to do to the results according to them physical activity that it is missing and physical inaction that it is being observed to say can _

Summary

1. Statistics , gerontology , age and sports physiology , health save eastern systems according to scientific books studied .

2. Health of gymnastics methodology work developed , scientific in terms of approved and results with based on research take went _ Traditional respectively applied hygienic gymnastics from exercises different as , health gymnastics exercises deep philosophy with separate stands and that's it because of not only physical maybe _ _ engaged in of people to the worldview too effect does _ This technique mature and old age people with training transfer for recommendation reach can _

3. Received hardware observations results as well anthropometric , measurements , functional indicators control to do based on work developed healthy gymnastics methodology according to training efficient said to the conclusion to arrive can.

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